

PEDAGOGICAL FEATURES OF IMPROVING STUDENTS' ARTISTIC THINKING IN THE CONTEXT OF CULTURAL EVENTS

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Annotation: In the article, the pedagogue who organizes cultural and educational events in higher education institutions helps and creates an opportunity for students to see the future clearly, to find ways to achieve it, to have high ideals, and to improve the artistic thinking of students.

Keywords: cultural event, thinking, artistic thinking, spiritual and educational, education and training, educational system, pedagogy.

Анотация. Мақолада олий таълим муассасаларида маданий-маърифий тадбирларни ташкил қилувчи педагог талабаларда ўзини-ўзи тарбиялашни йўлга қўйиши учун уларга истиқболни аниқ кўра билишларида, унга эришиш йўлларини излаб топишида, юксак идеалларга эга бўлишларида ёрдам бериши ва имконият яратиши ва талабаларнинг бадиий тафаккурини такомиллаштиришнинг педагогик хусусиятлари масаласи ёритилган.

Калит сўзлар: маданий тадбир, тафаккур, бадиий тафаккур, маънавий-маърифий, таълим ва тарбия, таълим тизими, педагогика.

Аннотация. В статье педагог, организующий культурно-просветительские мероприятия в высших учебных заведениях, помогает и создает возможность студентам ясно видеть будущее, находить пути его достижения, иметь высокие идеалы, совершенствовать художественное мышление студентов.

Ключевые слова: культурное событие, мышление, художественное мышление, духовно-просветительское, воспитание и воспитание, воспитательная система, педагогика.

National education plays an important role in the formation of artistic thinking of young people. Historical pictures are the center of national education, the influence in the image, the reflection of the event in history in the visual world, the visual solution, professional cinematography shakes the emotions.

Speaking about education and training, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoev – “Another issue that will never lose its relevance and importance for us is that our children are independent-minded, possess modern knowledge and skills, have a strong life position, and truly it is the task of

educating people as patriots” [1; p. 103] - it is no secret that the issue of youth education is becoming more important.

Education plays an important role in the development of a person, in the life of young people. Everyone is educated in the family, the people educates the artist. The development of the artistic thinking of young people is directly connected with work, public recognition, and the growth of artistic aesthetic consciousness. If thinking develops in the form of spiritual structures, consciousness will have an emotional content as a product of thinking in addition to intellectual cognition. [2; p. 23].

The national encyclopedia of Uzbekistan explains the word thinking in the following way – “Thinking is the highest form of objective perception of the world, reflected in concepts, theories, etc., the important connections and relationships of things and events, creating new theories, ideas, predicting future processes, etc. is an active process. Thought appears in the process of people’s social production activity and it appears as a product of social development” [4; p. 257].

Patterns of artistic thinking are a wide-ranging, multifaceted social phenomenon, and are used in the sense of creative reflection of existence and social reality by means of artistic symbols. In scientific-philosophical literature, it is interpreted as things created by human labor, intelligence, and consciousness. The directions of influence of artistic thinking, as a spiritual phenomenon, on social development are studied by a number of disciplines on the basis of specific principles. At this point, it can be said that the organization of spiritual and educational activities related to reading in higher education institutions is one of the most effective ways to improve students’ artistic thinking. Because a person realizes his identity by reading a book, a sense of national pride is formed. Because the book is a tool of thinking, a key to treasures, a source of thought, our people considered it as dear, honorable and sacred as bread.

That’s why the pedagogue who organizes cultural and educational events in higher education institutions should help and create opportunities for students to see the future clearly, to find ways to achieve it, to have high ideals, in order to start self-education in students. In this regard, the pedagogue should consider the formation and development of the national characteristics of our people in students through cultural and educational activities.

Cultural activities carried out in the educational system can be divided into the following two types:

1. Activities conducted in the course of direct education. They include types of cultural events used in the form of lessons, such as lectures, seminars, and practical training. When using this type of events, excerpts from monologues, stagings, artistic works, video and audio recordings are presented during the lessons. These activities help to deepen the study of the subject, course or subject. At the same time, these events can serve as a short-term break for students during the course of the lesson.

2. Extracurricular activities. They include themed evenings, debates of sharp minds, creative meetings, scientific debates, evenings, discussions, scientific and creative conferences, theatrical concerts, public performances, entertainments, holidays, carnivals, pageants, trips, excursions, Olympiads, exhibitions, fun includes games, artistic and sports events, artistic amateur circles and others. [3; pp. 49-50].

During the preparation of the plan of the lesson (educational event), the teacher creates an image of the actions performed in these processes in his imagination. A pedagogue should be able to correctly and rationally choose the methods that ensure the effective course of the pedagogical process in planning his professional activity or training. [5; p. 29].

Cultural events aimed at forming the artistic thinking of young people will be more appropriate if they are organized with the help of dramatized films in the form of conversation, question-answer, debate, story. The purpose of the activities conducted during the training is to deepen understanding of the topic studied in this training, to serve for better remembering.

Therefore, in modern conditions, it is necessary for a pedagogue to constantly search for himself, to develop his creativity, to be able to form the skills of creating creative products related to the educational or educational process.

In short, the human psyche and creative thinking are nourished by the seeds of enlightenment. In our technologically advanced age, paying attention to reading, realizing that spirituality and enlightenment are a powerful force, developing the artistic thinking of young people through mature works of art opens the door to great goals in the future. The more meaningful and active the minds of young people are, the more rational and consistent, the higher the level of inventions and creative thinking and professional behavior.

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